

Should we pursue municipal mergers? A systematic literature review on the effect of municipal mergers

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Summary

1. We provide a literature review on municipal merger research over the past two decades.
2. 15 European countries implemented municipal reforms during the decade 2008-2017, resulting in a reduction of more than 5,000 European municipalities.
3. In terms of economic effects, most studies observe that although municipal mergers will significantly reduce administrative expenditures, they will not likewise significantly reduce the total expenditure of local governments.
4. In terms of democratic effects, municipal mergers have significant adverse effects. On the one hand, the expansion of jurisdictions increases the political and physical distance between voters and politicians, whilst voters have a lower sense of local identity; on the other hand, it becomes more difficult for governments in large jurisdictions to satisfy heterogeneous preferences.
5. In terms of management effects, municipal mergers usually do not improve public services and administrative efficiency but make efforts to create a vision, serve the mayor, and maintain external relations.

1. Introduction

Municipal mergers are a universal phenomenon in the world. Since World War II, developed and developing countries have implemented municipal mergers of different scales. The United States has a long historical

tradition in the reform of city-county mergers. Especially after the Great Depression in the United States, city-county mergers were increasingly considered (Stenberg, 2011). Since the merger of New Orleans and New Orleans Parish became the first city-county

merger case in 1815, in the following nearly 200 years, local governments in the United States have made about 166 attempts and successfully implemented 39 city-county merger reforms (Martin & Schiff, 2011). Hall et al. (2020) updated the number of successful cases to 41 and argued that attempts at city-county mergers are still popular with local governments. According to Swianiewicz (2018), 15 European countries implemented municipal reforms during the decade 2008-2017, although the current territorial restructuring reform has become one of the most challenging reforms in the field of political reform. The merger policy has resulted in a reduction of more than 5,000 European municipalities. Furthermore, municipal mergers happened in Asia (e.g., China, Japan) and Africa (e.g., South Africa) (Tang & Hewings, 2017; Yamada & Arai, 2021; Goto et al., 2021).

While municipal mergers are widely practiced as a public policy, its effectiveness has been questioned. On the one hand, proponents believe that municipal mergers can effectively borrow economies of scale, reduce spillover effects and improve resource allocation efficiency (Oates, 1997). On the other hand, the increase in municipality size raises concerns about diseconomies of scale, as an increased size may raise expenditures such as agency and information costs (Allers & Geertsema, 2016). Larger organizations typically require more planning, monitoring, and reporting than smaller organizations. In addition, the reduction in the number of political districts is also believed to reduce scale competition and weaken development incentives for local officials (Allers, 2012). Considering the positive and negative effects of municipal mergers, the study of municipal mergers, including their motives and effects, has always been a classic and widely debated proposition in political science, economics, public administration, and geography. In this

policy brief, we conduct a systematic review of empirical papers on the effect of municipal mergers over the past few decades, analyzing their number of publications, case distribution, research areas, consensus and controversy of results, and research methods.

2. Methods

We focus on sorting out the existing empirical evidence on the impact of municipal mergers. Our search platform is fully based on the Web of Science (WoS) database. The search took place in August 2022 and returned 199 relevant documents. Through the manual reading of the above literature (see Figure 1), we filtered out the articles that (1) concentrate on theoretical issues or do not provide policy effects assessment (113 papers), (2) study single-sector or village-scale consolidation cases (8 papers), and (3) are concerned with the pre-assessment of municipal mergers (9 papers). Our empirical articles employ diverse data (such as statistics, questionnaires, and interviews) using qualitative or quantitative methods. Also, we obtained 20 relevant pieces of literature by the snowball method. Finally, 89 empirical papers on the performance analysis of municipal mergers are accepted. Our analysis in the following sections relies on these papers.

Fig.1 Selection criteria

3. Results

Municipal merger policy has always been widely valued by governments and society and practiced in many countries worldwide. From the perspective of published literature, although the number of papers published has increased in recent years, the total amount is still small, especially the lack of empirical research. This systematic literature review analyzes the existing empirical papers on the impact assessment of municipal mergers and sorts out the existing research growth trends, case distribution, research areas, consensuses and controversies in research conclusions, and methodology. It attempts to propose the possible reasons for the existence of controversies. This will have particular reference significance for the decision-making reference of local governments.

We draw three main conclusions from a review of the 89 selected empirical papers.

Research trends. The number of research papers on municipal mergers is increasing, most of which are in Western developed countries and Japan. In contrast, research in developing countries is mainly found in China. Research on municipal mergers in

developed countries focuses on local government spending, common pools, economic growth, public services, administrative efficiency, and citizens' political participation and satisfaction. In developing countries, they pay more attention to economic growth, environmental governance, and land use. This reflects the differentiated policy goals of developed and developing countries when implementing municipal mergers.

Mainstream views. *In terms of economic effects*, most studies observe that although municipal mergers will significantly reduce administrative expenditures, they will not likewise significantly reduce the total expenditure of local governments. Existing direct studies on municipal mergers do not provide an optimal population size for municipal mergers, because the threshold of economies of scale in different countries is affected by various factors such as geographical environment, political system, level of economic development, and implementation process of merger policies. Unlike the post-consolidation subnational government spending, the common pool highlights changes in individual subnational governments' expenditure (or debt) before the merger. On the common pool, most of the existing studies show that “municipalities change the intertemporal budget allocation by increasing their debt issuance before mergers and they consider that this debt issuance is induced by the “fiscal common pool problem” because of pooled budgets after mergers.” (Akia et al., 2022, p. 307). However, social norms and corresponding regulatory measures can effectively control the common pool problem. Finally, the literature underscores the variegated impact of municipal mergers on the economic growth of western and developing countries, with

positive effects for the latter and statistically insignificant effects for the former.

In terms of democratic effects, municipal mergers have significant adverse effects. On the one hand, the expansion of jurisdictions increases the political and physical distance between voters and politicians, whilst voters have a lower sense of local identity; on the other hand, it becomes more difficult for governments in large jurisdictions to satisfy heterogeneous preferences. Regarding electoral representativeness, we must pay special attention to the merger of large and small cities. After the merger, the large cities will take the lead, quickly reducing small towns to a peripheral and subsidiary role for large cities. Research by Bhatti and Hansen (2019) reminds us that turnout increases during the early stages of mergers may be due to electoral efforts by old municipalities to secure influence in new cities.

In terms of management effects, municipal mergers usually do not improve public services and administrative efficiency but make efforts to create a vision, serve the mayor, and maintain external relations. In addition, recent studies have also found that municipal mergers positively affect environmental protection, energy conservation and construction land expansion.

Possible sources of controversy and methodology. The literature is not free of controversies and methodological debates. The conclusions drawn from the empirical assessment of municipal mergers are far from homogenous, due to – among others – differences in policy implementation background, data validity, variable selection, and research methods. The current empirical research has transformed from simple descriptive analysis to regression analysis.

With the development of new research methods and data availability, contemporary empirical research has given more consideration to endogenous issues and adopted more complex econometric models, such as Difference-in-Differences model, synthetic control method and structural equation model, etc. However, this methodological progress varies across different topics, with some studies using interview and questionnaire data that lack the rigor of causal identification.

4. Policy Recommendations

Municipal consolidation has attracted the interest of policy makers, politicians, and the academic community. Despite the fact that the literature has drawn ambiguous and, in some instances, even contradictory conclusions, in this section we provide three policy recommendations that could become reference-points for formulating relevant policies for municipal merger reforms.

The central government. In most countries, municipal consolidation is usually a top-down process. The central government is not only the promoter of reform but also the supervisor of the reform process. Studies have shown that the central government can control and avoid the common pool problem through effective regulation and legislation. In addition, the central government needs to consider more alternatives to municipal consolidation reform. Generally, municipal merger policies face relatively high economic and political costs, risks, and disputes. Existing empirical studies mostly observe that mergers have reduced the political participation of local citizens. The choice of cooperation between cities (Carr & Feiock, 2004) can be regarded as a more powerful means. For example, existing studies have shown that municipal cooperation in Italy has achieved good results, which has reduced per

capita expenditure without reducing the level of local public services (Ferraresi et al., 2018). The special district government has become an alternative to the merger of cities and counties in the United States and is used to undertake or solve certain public affairs (McCabe, 2016). Given the significant impact of global events on people's lives (e.g., Covid-19 pandemic), societies have begun to re-examine the pros and cons of big government and the distribution of urban scale. Against this background, the central government should approach municipal merger reform more cautiously.

Local government. The local government is the main body of the municipal merger and the specific maker of the merger plan. Local governments should realize that not all services in big cities have the potential for economies of scale. Capital-intensive services represented by urban infrastructure have good potential for economies of scale. In contrast, labor-intensive services directly related to citizens usually do not have the potential for economies of scale. The formulation of the merger plan should be based on the scientific understanding of the problems in the city itself. Furthermore, most studies show that mergers among many small cities have a greater probability of achieving economies of scale, avoiding “exploitation of the great by the small” and electoral representational imbalances than mergers between large cities and small cities.

Research scholars. Future researchers need to standardize the research paradigm of empirical papers, including using precise and reliable research data, representative research variables, and selecting rigorous and diverse methods to identify the causal effects of policies. However, it seems that the appropriate research methods are limited at present. This needs to be further expanded for

classical methods such as DID model and synthetic control method.

Researchers should combine the economic effects, democratic effects, and management effects of municipal mergers to evaluate the benefits and risks of municipal merger policies comprehensively. When the existing literature studies local government expenditure or public services, most of them are considered separately. Few studies directly examine municipal mergers' impact on urban administrative efficiency. But more are indirect assessments, that is, the policy is the background rather than a variable, such as examining the effects of population size on public services in the context of combined policies (D'Inverno et al., 2020). Further, we see little research on combined effects, where economic and democratic effects are usually assessed separately. In this regard, the use of new comprehensive indicators and efficiency analysis methods (D'Inverno & De Witte, 2020) is an important trend in evaluating future municipal mergers' complete effects.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

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